

DETERMINANTS OF NURSE PERFORMANCE USING EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY AT A VERTICAL HOSPITAL IN DKI JAKARTA PROVINCE

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze and address the research gaps in various previous studies. Furthermore, there is a phenomenon where Employee Engagement functions as an inconsistent intervening variable that can explain Employee Performance, in this case Nurse Performance. These factors are the reasons for conducting this study. This research is a quantitative descriptive study using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method in the LISREL application. The research object used in this study is employee engagement in vertical hospitals in DKI Jakarta province with a population of 4,931 people and a sample size of 370. The results of this study indicate that all exogenous variables in this study can significantly explain their influence and are positively correlated with endogenous variables, where the dominant variable in the first model is Organizational Commitment, while in the second model is Employee Engagement. These results are expected to assist management in organizing and maximizing its human resources.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Quality of Work of Life, Organizational Commitment, Employee Engagement, Nurse Performance.

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The rapid advancement of information technology in the era of Industry 4.0, or the era of modernization, in Indonesia and around the world has resulted in increasingly fierce business competition in all sectors. Furthermore, the digital era allows for rapid information dissemination worldwide through internet technology. This is evident in the rapid dissemination of information worldwide regarding the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019-2020. The public can also easily and quickly access various information they need.

This level of competition is also felt and experienced by hospitals in Indonesia. This level of competition can encourage hospital management to improve and implement various policies to face the competition. Efforts made by a company or organization involve internal and external improvements. Internal improvements can include increasing its resources. One such resource is human resources, specifically nurses. Nurses can be managed and developed to be more productive. High nurse performance can ultimately improve organizational performance and achieve organizational goals.

Vertical hospitals in the DKI Jakarta province are also experiencing the impact of intense competition in the digital era. Therefore, various policies and strategies are needed from the management of vertical hospitals in DKI Jakarta to overcome competition by managing and improving their resources. Vertical hospitals are hospitals directly managed by the Ministry of

Health. Vertical hospitals in the DKI Jakarta area are Dr. Cipto Mangunkusumo National Central General Hospital or RSCM (Central Jakarta), Persahabatan Hospital (East Jakarta), Fatmawati Hospital (South Jakarta), Harapan Kita Heart and Blood Vessel Hospital (West Jakarta), and Sulianti Saroso Hospital (North Jakarta).

Performance is the result of work related to organizational goals, such as quality, efficiency, and other aspects of effectiveness (Gibson et al., 2012). Nurse performance is the nurse's ability to perform a specific skill. Nurse performance is crucial because it determines their ability to carry out assigned tasks (Sinambela, 2016).

Performance, or work achievement, in a somewhat limited sense, is often used to measure an individual's work performance, for example, tasks assigned to someone within the company legally, legally, and in accordance with established standards and ethics. Nurse performance requires extra consideration from company management, considering that declining nurse performance can lead to decreased organizational or company performance. Therefore, maximum efforts are needed to improve nurse performance.

Many factors can influence nurse performance, including organizational citizenship behavior, organizational culture, leadership style, training, discipline, employee engagement, quality of work life, organizational commitment, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, competence, work environment, and so on. These factors that can influence nurse performance require management's attention. Nurse performance, in this study, can be influenced by employee engagement.

Engagement is defined as a positive, meaningful, and motivated attitude, characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Vigor is characterized by high levels of energy, resilience, a desire to strive, and persistence in the face of challenges. Dedication is characterized by feelings of worth, enthusiasm, inspiration, value, and challenge. Absorption is characterized by full concentration on a task (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2010).

The number of nurses who resigned at a vertical hospital in DKI Jakarta from 2017 to 2019 was high compared to established resignation standards. This indicates that nurses' employee engagement with the hospital is still suboptimal. Interviews revealed that most nurses resigned due to their husbands transferring to other hospitals. During the COVID-19 pandemic, nurses interacted directly with patients on the front lines. Nurses' dedication to carrying out their high-risk duties amidst the pandemic is a key strength in the fight against COVID-19 in Indonesia.

The role of nurses is crucial; doctors cannot work alone without the support of nurses. Nurses work so comprehensively that nurses can actually be motivators at the beginning of the pandemic, the advocacy of nurses is extraordinary in preventing the emergence of negative stigma for Covid-19 patients, as conveyed by Dr. Sugiyanto, S.Pd, M.App.Sc, Head of the Health Human Resources Education Center of the Ministry of Health in giving his appreciation on the 47th anniversary of the Indonesian National Nurses Association (PPNI) on March 17, 2021.

Likewise, Harif Fadillah, Chairman of PPNI, also expressed his appreciation to nurses who are still struggling to overcome the pandemic, and in general, the task of nurses is to provide nursing care both during the pandemic and before the pandemic, although it has its own challenges during a pandemic like the current one, such as the nature of the disease is easily transmitted, so nurses must be more careful, alert, and disciplined. Before facing patients, nurses receive additional supplies through training to avoid transmission, including basic life support training. Nurses also provide motivation to patients to increase their will to recover, independence, including providing encouragement to patients. The large number of patients also provides a greater burden than usual, but nurses are always motivated in their work. This aligns with the findings of Miladiyah, Mustikasari, and Gayatri (2015), who stated that there is a relationship between motivation and nurse performance. This finding is supported by Badi'ah (2009), who stated that the higher the nurse's motivation, the better their performance. Nurses with high levels of employee engagement feel a sense of belonging to the company, a desire to progress with the organization, and a sense of pride in the company. Nurses with high levels of employee engagement can work with enthusiasm, which improves nurse performance and helps achieve company goals.

This is consistent with research conducted by Anitha (2013), Allameh et al. (2014), and Dajani (2015), which stated that employee engagement significantly influences nurse performance. This study identified several factors that can influence employee engagement, which in turn impacts nurse performance: transformational leadership, quality of work life, and organizational commitment. Transformational leadership is a process in which people engage with others and create relationships that enhance motivation and morale in both leaders and followers. This leadership is attentive to the needs and motives of followers and seeks to help followers achieve their full potential (Northouse, 2013).

According to Tajasom et al. (2015), transformational leaders help their followers achieve the organization's goals and mission by working with and through them. They empower their followers by influencing their beliefs, values, attitudes, and behaviors. Transformational leaders motivate their followers in ways that go beyond rewards and exchanges. Transformational leadership theory provides evidence that when a leader uses a transformational leadership style, it generates emotional attachment in followers or nurses toward the leader. The quality of a transformational leader can be assessed by the impact the leader has on followers.

Transformational leadership, when properly implemented in an organization, can influence nurses' work morale, motivation, job satisfaction, and trust in their leaders, making them more enthusiastic about achieving organizational goals. This will impact nurse engagement and improve nurse performance. Poorly implemented leadership, such as policies that disregard nurses, can lead to decreased work morale, motivation, job satisfaction, and trust in their leaders. This is consistent with research conducted by Bezuidenhout and Schultz (2013), Sougui et al. (2015), and Taran et al. (2009), which states that transformational leadership influences employee engagement and nurse performance.

Another factor that can influence employee engagement and nurse performance is quality of work life. Quality of work life is an effective program for improving working conditions (from the nurse's perspective) and greater organizational effectiveness (from the manager's perspective). Quality of work life also plays a role in monitoring nurses' work quality, and it helps managers generate ideas for improvements within an organization (Parvar et al., 2013). Bernardin and Russel (2003:520) state that quality of work life relates to the level of satisfaction, motivation, involvement, and personal commitment experienced in relation to their lives at work.

Organizations or companies can improve nurses' quality of work life by instilling a sense of comfort, fairness, democracy, pride, and responsibility. A sense of security, fairness, work motivation, and job satisfaction can impact employee engagement and nurse performance. This is consistent with research conducted by Fatmasari (2018), Thakur and Sharma (2019), Rusdin (2015), and Parangain-angin et al. (2020), Leitao, Pereira & Gonçalves (2019), Daniel (2019), Muhammadi and Karupiah (2019) stated that quality of work life influences employee engagement and nurse performance. In addition to transformational leadership and quality of work life, another factor influencing employee engagement and nurse performance is organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is the degree to which a nurse identifies with a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in that organization (Robbins and Coulter, 2015).

A high level of organizational commitment among nurses creates a sense of comfort in working within the organization, enabling nurses to work with enthusiasm and passion, and enabling nurses to complete work according to company targets to achieve organizational goals. High nurse commitment to the organization can lead to high employee engagement and nurse performance. This is in accordance with research conducted by Trofimov et al., (2017), Khalid and Khalid (2015), Ahmad (2014), Rafiei et al., (2014), Mohammadi and Karupiah (2019), Leitao et al (2019), which states that organizational commitment has an influence on employee engagement and nurse performance.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: Transformational Leadership (KT) influences Employee Engagement (EE).

H₂: Quality of Work of Life (QWL) influences Employee Engagement (EE).

H₃: Organizational Commitment (OC) influences Employee Engagement (EE).

H₄: There is an influence of Transformational Leadership (KT) on Nurse Performance (KP).

H₅: There is an influence of Quality of Work of Life (QWL) on Nurse Performance (KP).

H₆: There is an influence of Organizational Commitment (KO) on Nurse Performance (KP).

H₇: There is an influence of Employee Engagement (EE) on Nurse Performance (KP).

- KT = Transformational Leadership
- QWL = Quality of Work of Life
- KO = Organizational Commitment
- EE = Employee Engagement
- KP = Nurse Performance

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative approach to hypothesis testing. The research object is employee engagement in vertical hospitals in DKI Jakarta Province, spanning the period of 2020.

The population of 4,931 employees engaged in vertical hospitals in DKI Jakarta Province. Furthermore, the researcher used a proportional random sampling technique. To determine the minimum sample size required, if the population size is known, the Slovin formula can be used, assuming a tolerable sampling error rate of 5% (Sugiono, 2016):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size, 4931

e = sampling error rate, which is 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{4931}{1 + 4931 (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = 369,987 \approx 370$$

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables of Transformational Leadership

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4
Transformational Leadership (ζ1)	Idealized Influence (X1)	1 Confidence 2 Pride 3 Trust	KT1-KT2 KT3-KT4 KT5-KT6
	Inspirational Motivation (X2)	1 Communication 2 Enthusiasm 3 Optimism	KT7-KT8 KT9-KT10 KT11-KT12
	Intellectual Stimulation (X3)	1 Creativity 2 Rationality 3 Problem Solving	KT13-KT14 KT15-KT16 KT17-KT18
	Individualized Consideration (X4)	1 Caring 2 Mentoring 3 Development	KT19-KT20 KT21-KT22 KT23-KT24

Table 2: Variables Operational Quality of Work of Life

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4
Quality of Work of Life (ζ2)	Adequate and fair compensation (X1)	1 Decent compensation 2 Fair compensation	QWL1-QWL2 QWL3-QWL4
	Safe and Healthy Environment (X2)	1 Work environment 2 Occupational health 3 Working hours	QWL5-QWL6 QWL7-QWL8 QWL9-QWL10
	Development of Human Capacity (X3)	1 Skills 2 Expertise 3 Autonomy	QWL11-QWL12 QWL13-QWL14 QWL15-QWL16
	Growth and Security (X4)	1 Job security 2 Personal development 3 Career advancement	QWL17-QWL18 QWL19-QWL20 QWL21-QWL22
	Social Integration (X5)	1 Sense of belonging 2 Engagement	QWL23-QWL24 QWL25-QWL26
	Social Relevance (X6)	1 Ethical behavior 2 Social responsibility	QWL27-QWL28 QWL29-QWL30

Table 3: Operational Variables of Organizational Commitment

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4
Organizational Commitment	Affective (X1)	1 Feeling happy 2 Feeling proud	KO1-KO2 KO3-KO4

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4
(ζ)		3 Feeling connected	KO5-KO6
		1 Well-being	KO7-KO8
	Sustainable (X2)	2 Recognition	KO9-KO10
		3 Health insurance	KO11-KO12
	Normative (X3)	4 Needing the company	KO13-KO14
		1 Unethical	KO15-KO16
2 Loyalty		KO17-KO18	
3 Staying put		KO19-KO20	
4 Profit		KO21-KO22	
		5 Obligation	KO23-KO24

Table 4: Operational Variables of Employee Engagement

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4
Employee Engagement (η ₁)	Vigor (X1)	1 Energy level	EE1-EE2
		2 Resilience	EE3-EE4
		3 Willingness to strive	EE5-EE6
		4 Persistence of giving up	EE7-EE8
	Dedication (X2)	1 Feeling of worth	EE9-EE10
		2 Enthusiasm	EE11-EE12
		3 Inspiration	EE13-EE14
		4 Valuable	EE15-EE16
		5 Challenging	EE17-EE18
	Absorbtion (X3)	1 Full attention to work	EE19-EE20
		2 High concentration	EE21-EE22
		3 Seriousness about work	EE23-EE24

Table 5: Operational Variables of Nurse Performance

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4
Nurse Performance (η ₂)	Work Quality (X1)	1 Accuracy	KP1-KP2
		2 Thoroughness	KP3-KP4
		3 Skills	KP5-KP6
		4 Cleanliness	KP7-KP8
	Work Quantity (X2)	1 Routine output	KP9-KP10
		2 Extra output	KP11-KP12
	Reliability (X3)	1 Instruction	KP13-KP14
		2 Ability	KP15-KP16
		3 Initiative	KP17-KP18
		4 Care	KP19-KP20
		5 Diligence	KP21-KP22
	Attitude (X4)	1 Behavior towards fellow nurses	KP23-KP24
		2 Behavior towards work	KP25-KP26
		3 Company cooperation	KP27-KP28

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 6: Score Range and Categories

Score	Score Interval	Category
1	0,00 – 0,99	Strongly Disagree / Very Bad / Very Low
2	1,00 – 1,99	Disagree / Bad / Low
3	2,00 – 2,99	Quite Agree / Quite Bad / Quite High
4	3,00 – 3,99	Agree / Good / High
5	4,00 – 4,99	Strongly Agree / Very Good / Very High

Source: Cooper & Schindler (2013)

Table 7: Summary of Test Results Between Latent Variables

No	Structural Path	Path Coefficient	t-Value	t-Criterion	Test Results
1	Transformational Leadership (KT) → Employee Engagement (EE)	0,25	1,99	1,96	Significant
2	Quality of Work of Life (QWL) → Employee Engagement (EE)	0,15	1,97	1,96	Significant
3	Organizational Commitment (KO) → Employee Engagement (EE)	0,48	4,08	1,96	Significant
4	Transformational Leadership (KT) → Nurse Performance (KP)	0,21	2,39	1,96	Significant
5	Quality Work of Life (QWL) → Nurse Performance (KP)	0,12	2,16	1,96	Significant
6	Organizational Commitment (KO) → Nurse Performance (KP)	0,19	2,19	1,96	Significant
7	Employee Engagement (EE) → Nurse Performance (KP)	0,48	9,60	1,96	Significant

Source: Processed data

Sub-Structural Equation 1

$$EE = 0,25*KT + 0,15*QWL + 0,48*KO, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0,28, R^2 = 0,72$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0,12) & (0,076) & (0,12) & (0,028) \\ 1,99 & 1,97 & 4,08 & 9,78 \end{matrix}$$

Sub-Structural Equation 2

$$KP = 0,21*KT + 0,12*QWL + 0,19*KO + 0,48*EE, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0,13, R^2 = 0,87$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0,050) & (0,087) & (0,054) & (0,085) & (0,014) \\ 9,60 & 2,39 & 2,16 & 2,19 & 9,47 \end{matrix}$$

Table 8: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coefficient/R2	t value	t - Criterion	Test Results
H1	$H_0 : \gamma_{11} = 0$	Transformational Leadership has no effect on Employee Engagement	0,25	1,99	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₁ is accepted. Transformational Leadership has an impact on Employee Engagement.
	$H_a : \gamma_{11} \neq 0$	Transformational Leadership Influences Employee Engagement				
H2	$H_0 : \gamma_{12} = 0$	Quality of Work of Life has no effect on Employee Engagement	0,15	1,97	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₂ is accepted. Quality of Work Life influences Employee Engagement.
	$H_a : \gamma_{12} \neq 0$	Quality of Work of Life influences Employee Engagement				
H3	$H_0 : \gamma_{13} = 0$	Organizational Commitment has no effect on Employee Engagement	0,48	4,08	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₃ is accepted. Organizational Commitment has an effect on Employee Engagement.
	$H_a : \gamma_{13} \neq 0$	Organizational Commitment Influences Employee Engagement				
H4	$H_0 : \gamma_{21} = 0$	Transformational Leadership has no effect on Nurse Performance	0,21	2,39	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₄ is accepted. Transformational Leadership has an effect on Nurse Performance.
	$H_a : \gamma_{21} \neq 0$	Transformational Leadership Influences Nurse Performance				
H5	$H_0 : \gamma_{22} = 0$	Quality of Work of Life does not affect Nurse Performance	0,12	2,16	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₅ is accepted. Quality of Work Life influences Nurse Performance.
	$H_a : \gamma_{22} \neq 0$	Quality of Work of Life influences Nurse Performance				
H6	$H_0 : \gamma_{23} = 0$	Organizational Commitment Does Not Influence Nurse Performance	0,19	2,19	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₆ is accepted. Organizational Commitment has an effect on Nurse Performance.
	$H_a : \gamma_{23} \neq 0$	Organizational Commitment				

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coefficient/R2	t value	t - Criterion	Test Results
		Influences Nurse Performance				
H7	$H_0: \beta_{21} = 0$	Employee Engagement has no effect on Nurse Performance	0,48	9,60	1,96	H ₀ is rejected and H ₇ is accepted. Employee Engagement influences Nurse Performance.
	$H_a: \beta_{21} \neq 0$	Employee Engagement influences Nurse Performance				

Source: Processed data

H₁: Transformational Leadership has a significant and positive effect on Employee Engagement.

H₂: Quality of Work Life has a positive and significant effect on Employee Engagement.

H₃: Organizational Commitment has a significant and positive effect on Employee Engagement.

H₄: Transformational Leadership has a significant and positive effect on Nurse Performance.

H₅: Quality of Work Life has a significant and positive effect on Nurse Performance.

H₆: Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Nurse Performance.

H₇: Employee Engagement has a significant and positive effect on Nurse Performance.

CONCLUSION

Organizational Commitment is the dominant variable in the Employee Engagement variable, while Employee Engagement is the dominant variable in the Nurse Performance variable in employee engagement in vertical hospitals in DKI Jakarta province, where the Employee Engagement variable can successfully mediate and explain its influence on the research problem, namely Nurse Performance.

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